

A discourse on Jain Goddess Ambika from Odisha at Victoria and Albert Museum, London

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In Jain pantheon there are references of several goddesses. They largely owed their origin from the earlier tradition of worshipping the Yaksis. They are semi- divine beings and are technically known as *Sasanadevis*¹. They are attendant spirits regarded as devotees of Jinas². Among them Ambika occupies a foremost position in the Jain tradition. She is the attendant of Neminatha, the 22nd Tirthankara and is variously named as Ambika, Ambai, Amba, Amra and Kushmandini. The word 'Ambika' literally means a mother and in Jainism she is the goddess of material prosperity, childbirth, childhood diseases and motherhood. She is also a source of protection against the evil forces of nature. The Jainas adopted her form from an early Yaksi named Bahuputrika meaning one who has many children. She is highly venerated in both the Jaina sects (Digambaras and Svetambaras) and is amply represented in several Jain religious sacred space. In this paper an attempt has been made to critically analyse the image of Ambika from Odisha preserved in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London in the light of its style and iconography and situate it within the broader repertoire of Ambika imagery in Jaina iconography.

Before delving into the image of our present discourse a few words may be said about the textual and iconographic features of Ambika which is essential for critically analysing our image. Ambika, as the name implies is a reflection of Mother Goddess of Brahmanical tradition. She is regarded as an Amnaya Goddess who gradually became a *Sasanadevi* associated with Jina Neminatha or Aristanemi. However, it is interesting to note that her association with Tirthankaras other than Neminatha is mentioned in the Svetambara text *Vividhatirtha- kalpa* of Jinaprabha Suri where she is mounted on a lion protecting the

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Tirtha of Mathura³. The text also mentions the myth associated with Ambika where she was supposedly born as a human being and was married to an orthodox Brahman Somabhata in the city of Kodinar in Saurashtra. They had two sons Siddha and Buddha. According to the story once Somabhata invited some Brahmanas to dinner on the occasion of the *sraddha* ceremony of his ancestors. But instead of giving food to the Brahmanas, Ambika gave the food to a mendicant who needed it to break his fast which he undertook for a month. For this act Somabhata drove Ambika out of his house. She left the place with her two sons. In her journey miracles happened to her. She found a dried mango tree full of ripe mangoes and a dry lake filled with water. It helped her to feed her sons. Then she rested under the shade of the mango tree. At home miracles also happened which opened the eyes of Somabhata and his mother. Somabhata came running after her to restore them to their house. But Ambika misjudged Somabhata's intention and jumped into a well with her sons. She was born in heaven as a *yaksi* devoted to Neminatha. Her husband soon died and was reborn as a lion, the *vahana* of Ambika. The Digambara version of the story is mentioned in the "*Yaksi-katha*" found in *Punyasrava-katha*. According to it Ambika was known as Agnila and her husband was Somasarman, a Brahmana of Girinagara. Their sons were Subhankara and Prabhankara. In this version it is stated that she left her husband in company of her two sons and a faithful maid servant and went to Urijyant hill where Varadatta, the sage whom she gave food for breaking the fast was living. Iconographically Ambika images can be two-handed, four-handed, eight-handed and having more than eight hands. The two-armed variety usually portray her as standing and sitting. Our sitting image of Ambika from Odisha at the Victoria and Albert Museum Collection belongs to the two-handed variety. Regarding this variety the textual reference of Jinaprabhasuri may be cited. He describes her in *Urijyantra - sthava*. He states " May Ambika, of golden colour, riding on a lion and accompanied by (her two sons) Siddha and Buddha and holding a bunch of mangoes in her hand, protect the Jaina Sangha from obstacles". In addition to this, there are other textual evidences from both the Svetambara and Digambara tradition which make reference of the iconography of Goddess Ambika. In case of the two-handed variety, Ambika is usually represented as mounted over a lion holding a mango branch and a child. At this juncture it may be pointed out that the mango tree does not only serve the mythological necessity. In fact, the mango tree symbolically represents fertility and thus is an apt inclusion in the framework of the Ambika icon. *Chaturvimsatika* portray Ambika as having two hands. According to *Pratisthanasaroddhara* Ambika are two armed. She holds a mango branch (*amralumbi*) in

one hand and her son Priyankara on the other. Her another son Subhankara stands closely under the shade of the mango tree. The text *Pratisthatilakam* also speaks on the same lines. *Aparajitaprccha* describes her as a two-armed *yaksi* holding a fruit in one hand and displaying the *varada mudra* on the other. Both her sons are required to be beside her of whom one is to be carried by Ambika in her lap. Some texts mention Ambika as two armed or four armed. According to *Pratisthasarasamgraha* of the Digambara tradition Ambika, referred as Kushmandini is mounted on a lion and has two or four arms. *Nirvanakalika* text of the Svetambaras conceive her as a goddess mounted on a lion and holding a citron and a *pasa* in her right hands and carrying her son and an *ankusa* on her left hands⁴. Similar description is found in *Devatamurtiprakaranam*⁵. However, some texts like *Mantradhiraikalpa* donot mention her as carrying a child. According to the text her sons Siddha and Buddha are projected near her waist. *Rupamandana*, a significant treatise on iconography mentions *nagapasa* instead of *pasa* as her attribute. On the other hand, *Pravacanasaroddhara* replace citron for the mango branch. *Ambika Nataka* states that one of her sons would be holding the finger of Ambika and the other will be carried by the goddess. In addition, she holds a fruit, a mango branch, *ankusa* and a *pasa*⁶. The tantrik text of the Digambaras mention Ambika as four armed seated on a lion. She is also conceived with eight arms holding a conch, disc, bow, *parasu*, tomara, sword, *pasa* and *kodrava*. *Ambika - Tantra*, a tantrik text describes the terrific form of Ambika⁷.

Coming to the image of our concern it may stated without doubt that the jaina deity Ambika preserved in the South Asia Gallery of the Victoria and Albert Museum, London can be considered as one of the finest representation of the goddess. It is from Odisha and is assigned to c 1150- 1200 CE which coincides with the Eastern Ganga period. It is carved in grey chlorite and measures 119X 58 X 30 cm. Its weight is about 290 kg and the museum exhibit number is IS.61.1963. In keeping with the iconographic prescription, this image shows Ambika with her two sons sitting under the mango tree with mangoes. She is gracefully draped in a translucent lower garment and is bedecked with ornaments. Her hair is beautifully dressed with festoons of pearls and pendants and tied in a side knot. According to Gauri Parimoo Krishnan her hair style emulates Odishan hairdo⁸. Her right hand holds a cluster of mangoes while her left hand supports one of her sons. Her other child stands on the pedestal playfully reaching up to his mother. The deity's vehicle or *vahana* is the lion which is a typical iconographic characteristic of Goddess Ambika. The lion is chiseled beneath the lotus pedestal. On the pedestal are chiseled a pair of kneeling adorents who can be the donors.

Above the goddess one can see a number of figures. Among them the one in the centre with the halo can be identified as meditating Tirthankara Neminatha. He is flanked by two guardians and a pair of celestial garland bearers. The presence of Tirthankara confirms the Jain affiliation of the image. Moreover, the carving of Jina Neminatha is a fitting inclusion in the image as it helps us in the identification of the deity (Pl 1).

Stylistically the figure of Ambika reveals her elegant feminine charm. She is carved with a lot of grace. The sensuousness is created by her slender waist, full hips and ample breasts. The linear rhythm expressed in ample turns and curves is praiseworthy. She sits in *lalitasana* posture with her right leg dangling down. Moreover, the sculpture reveals the quintessential nature of a mother expressed by her protective stance towards her son positioned on her lap. The touching playful attitude of her second son to reach his mother indicates the emotional attachment a mother enjoys with her child. It may be emphasized that such features of motherhood were an obvious inclusion in the sculpture as the image was meant to highlight the concept of divine motherhood that the goddess stood for in the Jaina pantheon.

A comparative analysis with some icono- plastic representations of Jaina Ambika with our image of study (Ambika in the Victoria and Albert Museum) may be attempted in order to situate our icon within the broader repertoire of Ambika imagery. However, our discussion will be limited to those Ambika images which share some icono- stylistic similitude with our image.

A number of interesting images of Ambika from Odisha speak of its rich Jain heritage. Among them some icons display iconographic and stylistic resemblance to our Ambika image. In this regard mention may be made of a much-defaced small image of a two-armed jaina Ambika deity found attached on the inner wall of the jagamohana of the Balunkesvara temple at Barala, district Puri. The image displays close similitude with our image from the Victoria and Albert Museum. Like our image the well decked deity is sculpted sitting in *lalitasana posture* over a double petalled lotus holding her son in her left lap and a mango twig in her right hand. Her hairdo also shows much resemblance with our image. The branches of the mango tree behind her head can be identified despite much abrasion. Devotees and lion below the pedestal can also be seen. Despite much damage, one cannot miss the bountiful and

self-content appeal of the deity which is so pronounced in our image at the Victoria and Albert Museum⁹.

Another two-armed image of Ambika preserved in the Ambika temple near the Khandagiri hills of Bhubaneswar, District Khorda in Odisha should be taken into consideration¹⁰. This image to a great extent resembles the Ambika sculpture housed in the Victoria and Albert Museum. Similar to our image the Ambika temple icon shows *lalitasana* posture with right leg pendant over a lotus pedestal. She is holding the baby in her left lap and a mango twig in her right hand. Like our image here too below her seat is the lion. However, the devotee in this specimen is chiseled on the right. In our image the devotee is sculpted on the left. A small effigy of Neminatha is noticed on the mango tree above the head of the deity. The mango tree is elaborately carved with mangoes like our image. Moreover, the curve of the tree shows striking similarity with our image. Though the deity's hairdo matches the Odishan Ambika image in the Victoria and Albert Museum, the presence of halo in the Khandagiri image is not seen in our image. Moreover Khandagiri Ambika's sophisticated sensuousness in her attenuated waist and ample bust, her soft smile, refined linear rhythm and finesse greatly matches our image. (Pl 2)

A partially abraded two armed Ambika datable to 13th century CE in the temple of Harishankaresvara in the village of Kuanrapur, district Kendrapara, Odisha shows some stylistic and iconographic similarity with our Ambika image. Here Ambika is seated in her conventional *lalitasana* posture over the lotus pedestal. A mango tree bearing fruits can be seen above the deity's head. The image carries her son in the left lap and holds *amralumbi* in the right hand just like our sculpture. Her second son, whose head is mutilated is seen standing in frontal position on her right side. In contrast to this the second son in the Victoria and Albert Museum specimen displays childish liveliness in his attempt to reach his mother. The lion below the pedestal do not portray the energy which we see in the Ambika image at Victoria and Albert Museum. Further the flying garland bearers in the Kendrapara image is not seen in the Ambika sculpture at Victoria and Albert Museum. Moreover, the refined sophistication and feminine charm witnessed in our Ambika image is nowhere seen in the Kendrapara image. Robustness to some extent is seen in the depiction of the Kendrapara image. However, the sensuous appearance of the deity and the stylized chiseling of the mango leaf come close to our image¹¹.

Another image of two-handed Jaina Ambika from the Narayana temple complex in Ada in the Balasore District, Odisha deserves mention. This image shows stylistic resonance with our image. However, unlike our image, the slab in which the image of Ambika is chiseled in Ada is divided into two segments. While the upper segment is occupied by seated diminutive Tirthankara Neminatha in *dhyanamudra*, the lower segment showcases bejeweled Ambika in a larger dimension. Other iconographic markers like deity's *lalitasana* posture, *amralumbi* in her right hand, child in her left hand, mango tree in the backside and the lion below the lotus pedestal are similar to our image. Her other son to her right also shares commonality with the Ambika deity in the Victoria and Albert Museum. The headress of the image also show striking similitude with our image. However, the child's posture is different. The mango tree with mangoes is realistically carved in the Ada example. In contrast the mango tree in our image is stylistically carved. Moreover, Neminatha's *lanchana*, that is, the wheel is prominently positioned in the centre of the lotus pedestal of the Tirthankara. This is not seen in our specimen from Odisha preserved in the Victoria and Albert museum. However the jewellery, hairdo and the dangling *amralumbi* perfectly matches our image. In spite of the partly abraded face, the graceful feminine charm that characterizes the Ambika image from Ada matches our image¹².
(Pl 3)

Quite similar in conception to the Ambika image from Ada is another beautifully sculpted icon from Balighat in Balasore, Odisha. The two-handed deity is chiseled on the lower panel of a rectangular slab, while the upper panel illustrate Jina Neminatha. She is possibly protecting the child with her partly mutilated left hand and the right is holding the *amralumbi*. She is seated on the double petalled lotus in a similar posture as our image. Another child below can be seen. The couchant lion below the pedestal also displays same stance as our Ambika image at the Victoria and Albert Museum. A devotee below the pedestal can also be seen. Above the head of the deity is the mango tree above which is a lotus pedestal. Jina Neminatha is placed above this pedestal. Herein lies a difference between the Balighat Ambika depiction and the image. In our image a small effigy of Neminatha is seen above, whereas in the Balighat depiction a large image of Neminatha is sculpted flanked by devotees. However, the stylized mango tree, jewellery and the physiognomy of the deity greatly matches our image¹³.

It can be undoubtedly stated that the images of Jaina Ambika from Odisha iconographically and stylistically show striking similarity with our Ambika image preserved in the Victoria and Albert Museum. However, considering the ample iconoplastic representations of jaina Ambika throughout the Indian subcontinent, it will not be unwise to delve into the icono- stylistic study of some Ambika deities found outside Odisha and attempt a comparative study between them and our image.

A beautiful representation of Ambika from Madhya Pradesh datable to 8th - 9th century CE preserved in the Royal Ontario Museum deserves special mention. The bejeweled deity is two handed like our image displaying *lalitasana* posture. However, unlike our Ambika at the Victoria and Albert Museum collection, the left leg is not dangling down. Rather it is placed on her mount, the lion. She supports her plump son with her left hand while the right holds the *amralumbi* quite like our image. Her other son beside her left leg peeps out. This gesture of the child is completely different from our image. She sits on the lotus pedestal which is not elaborately carved like our Odishan image. Unlike our image, this representation in the Royal Ontario collection is a haloed deity. The lion mount with its tense muscular paw is more life- like than our image. The submissive attitude reflected in the figure of lion in the Ambika figure from Madhya Pradesh is praiseworthy. The detailed depiction of the mango tree with mangoes is realistically chiseled. It gives the appearance of a canopy which is blossoming with mangoes. This concept is totally absent in our image. Unlike our image, the Ambika from Madhya Pradesh do not chisel the Jina. In contrast to the frontal position of our goddess, the image in the Royal Ontario Museum shows slight twist of the waist which brings dynamism in this superb artwork. Though iconographic marker of Ambika from Madhya Pradesh resembles our image, but stylistic parameters show some difference. In fact the Ambika from Madhya Pradesh closely resemble feminine forms that existed in Central India in the early medieval period. She is represented as a stunningly beautiful goddess whose half closed eyes adds spirituality to the figure. While our Ambika at the Victoria and Albert Museum collection reveals a harmonious blend between earthy (emotional bond between mother and child) and spiritual (feeling of divinity), the Madhya Pradesh image is purely spiritual¹⁴.

A partially abraded and mutilated two handed images of Ambika from Madhya Pradesh preserved in the Himachal State Museum, Shimla may be taken into consideration. It is datable to 10th - 11th century CE. The deity holds *amralumbi* in her right hand while the left

hand holds the child like our specimen in the Victoria and Albert Museum. However the *amralumbi* do not dangle down like our image. Moreover, the mango tree and Jina is also absent. It may be conjectured that the tree might have been carved above the head of the deity when the image was intact. Quite similar to our image she sits in *lalitasana* posture on the lotus pedestal with the lion beneath her. She rests her leg on the lotus petaled cushion which is absent in our image. This image displays sensuousness with ample breasts and rounded contours indicating the element of fertility. Her inner serenity radiates calm and peacefulness. This creates spirituality in the figure like the above example from Madhya Pradesh. But the feeling of content motherhood evidently displayed in the image in Victoria and Albert Museum collection is not seen here¹⁵.

An image of two armed seated Ambika from Rajgir is mention worthy. It is placed at the porch of temple no.3 at Vaibharagiri. The image is datable to 8th century CE. Here bejeweled Ambika is seated holding a bunch of mangoes with her right hand and her standing child tries to reach it, a stance similar to our image. Above is the mango tree with fruits. She holds the other child on her lap. She sits in *lalitasana* like our image. However, the lotus pedestal chiseled in our image is not found here. Her *vahana*, the lion is behind her right leg quite similar to the image of our study. However, the alert look of the lion in Rajgir example is not visible in our image. Moreover, the elegant grace of the Odishan Ambika with remarkable linear rhythm is missed in the Rajgir image¹⁶.

A richly carved haloed image of Goddess Ambika from Shahabad District, Bihar deserves special mention. It is preserved in the Los Angeles County Museum of Art and datable to 6th century CE. It is made of sandstone. It is four armed unlike our two handed Odishan image in the Victoria and Albert Museum. Like our image she sits in the usual *lalitasana* posture on a lion. However, in this image the left leg falls down instead of the dangling right leg as seen in our Ambika image. Moreover, the deity sits on the submissive *vahana* with her right knee resting on the head of the lion. This is a completely different stance as compared to our image. She supports a plump baby on her left thigh like our image. Unfortunately, the baby's head is mutilated. The other left hand of the deity is broken. The right lower hand holds a *matulinga* (lemon) and right upper hand holds a bunch of *amralumbi*. The other child is not seen here. Unlike our image the Jina and the mango tree is not represented in the Bihar image. Her jewellery is quite different from our image. The calm graceful gesture of the deity with a soft smile and half-closed eyes brings divine elegance

in this masterpiece. This calm gracefulness resonates with our image. However, the indelible stamp of regional specification remains prominent in the Bihar sculpture¹⁷. (Pl 4)

Rajasthan too has ample specimens of jaina heritage. With regard to Ambika image mention may be made of a beautiful figure of the Goddess in marble datable to 13th century CE from Dilwara group of Temples at Mt Abu. It is sculpted in the niche. The framework of this beautiful piece is different from our image. The head of the image from Mt Abu is surrounded by mango tree with bunches of mangoes. Like our image, here too the goddess holds the child with her left hand. The child fondly touches her breast. Another child stands below beside the couchant lion. Unlike the round gracefulness of our Odishan image, the Mt Abu specimen reveals a squarish face with leg flexed sharply at the knee and the garment. In fact, the regional style dominates the conception, framework and decorative details of the icon¹⁸. (Pl 5)

The cave temples of Ellora are considered as one of the most significant monuments showcasing rich Jaina heritage. Here several jain Ambika images have been recovered. Among them a beautiful representation of Ambika chiseled in the Ellora cave. No 33 is an interesting one. It is belonging to mid-8th century CE. In the two-armed image the deity displays its characteristic *lalitasana* posture like our image and rests on a lotus. The elaborate lotus pedestal as we see in our image is not seen in this specimen at Ellora. Unfortunately, her hands are broken. A mutilated plumpy child stands by her left side. A mango tree with fruits and bird is chiseled above. It is completely different from the Ambika image at Victoria and Albert Museum. Another deviation from our image is the oval halo above which is the effigy of Neminatha. Unlike our image the lion at Ellora is carved with a lot of elaboration. Its gaping mouth, stylized mane with tense muscular development reveals the ample energy of the beast. The deity is flanked by a number of male and female devotees in different postures. This feature stands in contrast to our image. Moreover, the deity does not sit in strict frontal position like our image, but shows slight right flexion. The soft grace of the deity to some extent bears akinness to our image¹⁹.

Another figure of two-handed Ambika from cave 33 of Ellora may be taken a note of. It is a mutilated image seated in a frontal position like our image. The Ambika figure from Ellora exhibits *lalitasana* posture like our image. However, in place of dangling right leg visualized in the Ambika at Victoria and Albert Museum, this image from Ellora shows the

left leg in the dangling position. Ambika sits with her left leg flexed over the body of the lying lion. Another deviation from our image is the presence of halo in the Ellora specimen. Goddess Ambika holds a child with her left hand like our image. However, the head of the child is broken. The other child stands by her right side. The right hand of the deity holds a bunch of mangoes. There is a conglomerate of mango leaves and fruits amidst which is a small effigy of the Jina. This is not seen in our image at Victoria and Albert Museum. The round and heavy spreading form noticeable in Ambika at Ellora extends beyond the principal figure and encompasses the entire composition with an expansive conception of plastic volume frequently seen in other reliefs at Ellora. Thus, the Ellora examples should be looked as a grand composition related to Goddess Ambika rather than simply an imagery of jaina goddess Ambika. Herein lies a difference with our Ambika image at Victoria and Albert Museum²⁰.

From a detailed analysis of the jaina Ambika from Odisha kept in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London it can be unquestionably stated that the image is one of the magnificent representations of its kind. The impeccable delineation of the iconographic features with a refined sense of aesthetic speaks greatly of a strong atelier under the guidance of which this masterpiece must have been produced. The stylistic minutiae showcased in the sculpture greatly resonate to the icono- stylistic idiom intrinsic to its core area, that is, Odisha. A comparative icono- stylistic analysis with some Ambika images from other parts of India substantiates our assumption. Moreover, the use of hard chlorite stone usually seen in the artistic production of Odisha is the material par excellence in our image. Chlorite stone gives an almost metallic finish to the image which is clearly noticeable in our Ambika image. Although generally speaking the timeframe of our image coincides with the rule of Eastern Gangas of Odisha, the absence of epigraphical data related with our image prevents us from ascertaining authorship and the nature of patronage so far as the original context of our sculpture is concerned.

Thus in the final analysis it may be stated that the jaina Ambika image from Odisha preserved in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London is one of the finest representation of the jaina Ambika sculptures so far retrieved from the Indian subcontinent. The radiant tenderness and quiet ease along with bountiful benevolence of a mother is beautifully accomplished in the sculpture. The detailed delineation of the iconographic features, the exquisite rendering of large and small figures, the skillful chiseling of ornaments and the

creation of the elegant feminine poise in the figure accentuates the religio-aesthetic effect of this icono- plastic marvel. In fact all praises fall short for this masterpiece and we are irresistibly absorbed in the realization of the metaphorical concept of the mother goddess that the deity stood for.

References

1. Tiwari Maruti Nandan Prasad (1983) *Elements of Jaina Iconography*, Indological Book House, Varanasi, p 77
2. *Ibid*, p 77
3. Bhattacharya A. K (2010) *Historical Development of Jaina Iconography*, Bharatiya Kala Prakashan, Delhi, p 51
4. Nagar Shantilal (1999) *Iconography of Jaina Deities*, Vol 1, B.R Publishing House, Delhi ,p 291
5. *Ibid*, p 291
6. *Ibid*, p 292
7. *Ibid*, p 293
8. Krishnan Gauri Parimoo (2006) 'Nature goddesses' in *Goddess: Divine Energy*, cat no 13, Sydney, pp 22- 27
9. Sahoo Ashis Ranjan (2015) *Jainism in Odisha(Orissa)*, www.wisdomlib.org, plate XCI.B
10. *Ibid*, plate LXXII.D
11. *Ibid*, plate LXI.B
12. *Ibid*, plate IV.B
13. Acharya Dipsikha (2017). 'Exploring Jaina Sculptural Remains from the Districts of Balasore and Bhadrak, Odisha, *Puravritta 2*, Directorate of Archaeology & Museums, West Bengal, Fig 12, pp 111-127
14. *Royal Ontario Museum (ROM) helloteri*, [https:// helloteri.com/](https://helloteri.com/) 2016/04/ 19/rom/
15. [https://pin.it/ 5WZ4T1U](https://pin.it/5WZ4T1U)
16. Bhattacharya A.K, *op.cit*, p 52 fig 1
17. Pal Pratapaditya (1994) *The peaceful liberators The Jaina Art in India*, Thames and Hudson, Los Angeles County Museum of Art, London p 176,fig 25
18. Bhattacharya A.K, *op.cit*, p 53,fig 11
19. *Ibid*, p 52 fig 2
20. *Ibid*, p 52 fig 3

Plates:

**Pl 1: Ambika, Odisha, Preserved in the Victoria and Albert Museum, London
(Photographed by the author)**

**Pl 2: Ambika, Jain Temple, Khandagiri Hill, Bhubaneswar, District Khorda, Odisha
(Photo Courtesy Ashis Ranjan Sahoo, 2015)**

**Pl 3: Ambika, Narayana Temple Complex, Ada, District Balasore, Odisha
(Photo Courtesy: Ashis Ranjan Sahoo, 2015)**

Pl 4: Ambika, Bihar (Photo courtesy Pratapaditya Pal, 1994)

Pl 5: Ambika, Dilwara, Mt Abu, Rajasthan (Photo Courtesy M.N.P Tiwari, 1989)